

an oil bath at 180-90° for 2 h. The gummy mass thus obtained was washed with 1 : 1 HCl (5 ml) and water and triturated with ethanol when the solid separated. The product was crystallised from ethanol (Table 2). IR (KBr) of IVa : 3250 (7-OH), 1720

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA OF IV

Compd.	R	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen %* Found (Calcd.)
IVa	H	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄	264-66	68	7.65 (7.69)
IVb	2-OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄	228-29	65	7.88 (7.40)
IVc	3-OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄	284-85	63	7.41 (7.40)
IVd	4-OH	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄	242-43	61	7.42 (7.40)
IVe	2-Cl	C ₁₁ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₄	247-48	69	7.00 (7.02)
IVf	3-Cl	C ₁₁ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₄	257-58	67	7.04 (7.02)
IVg	4-Cl	C ₁₁ H ₉ ClN ₂ O ₄	252-58	65	7.05 (7.02)

* C and H analyses were found to be satisfactory.

(lactonic CO) and 1650 (-CON). PMR (DMSO-d₆) of IVa : 3.26 (4H, t, -CH₂N(CH₂)₂), 3.68 (4H, t, Ar-N(CH₂)₂), 4.0 (2H, s, 4-CH₂CON<), 6.12 (1H, s, C₈H) and 6.7-7.6 (8H, m, ArH).

Pharmacology :

The compounds were tested on mice (albino mice of Haffkin strain) for their expected CNS action in CMC suspension. All the compounds were found to be inactive even at the high dose of 900 mg/kg.

Inhibition of edema produced by carrageenin (0.1 ml of 1% Ca-carrageenin in normal saline, subcutaneous) in the hind paw of rats was measured by the standard method¹⁴. Phenylbutazone was used as the standard and % inhibition of the edema by the test compounds as well as by the standard as compared with the control was recorded (Table 1). Compounds III showed the activity during the first hour of administration. meta-Substitution of the N-phenyl ring of piperazine was found to be favourable and m-Cl was the most effective. Compounds IV showed no antiinflammatory activity.

References

- V. N. GUPTA, B. R. SHARMA and R. B. ARORA, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 3000.
- G. M. CINGOLANI, F. GUALTIERI and M. PIGINI, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1969, 12, 531.
- D. S. BARIANA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1970, 13, 544.
- R. B. DESAI, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 5251.
- D. R. PAOLO, L. VERLICCHI and I. SETNIKAR, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, 25, 1097.
- M. G. PATEL and S. SETHNA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 39, 595.
- S. KUMAR and S. S. JOSHI, *Indian J. Appl. Chem.*, 1968, 26, 149.
- S. KUMAR and S. S. JOSHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 42, 57.

- D. R. PAOLO, G. BONALA and L. VERLICCHI, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, 7, 162.
- J. N. GADRE, Ph. D. Thesis, University of Bombay, 1981.
- C. B. POLLARD and T. H. WICKER, JR., *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 1853.
- S. C. LASKOWSKI and R. O. OLINTON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 3927.
- K. G. NAIK, R. D. DESAI and H. R. DESAI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 83.
- G. A. WINTER, F. A. RISLEY and G. W. NUSS, *Proc. Soc. Expt. Biol. Med.*, 1962, 111, 544.

Synthesis and Pharmacological Activities of New 3-Phenyl-3(N,N-substituted aminomethyl)-2(3H)-benzofuranones

H. G. S. RATHORE and V. MALLA REDDY*

Medicinal Chemistry Laboratories, University College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Kakatiya University, Warangal-506 009

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3-PHENYL-2(3H)-benzofuranone, a γ -lactone, has been proved to be a potent pharmacophore for anticonvulsant activity¹. Some derivatives of 3-phenyl-2(3H)-benzofuranone containing a basic moiety have been found to exhibit musculotropic, anaesthetic and antispasmodic properties²⁻⁴. Amethone, 3-phenyl-3(β -diethylaminoethyl)-2(3H)-benzofuranone is used against bronchial asthma and at the same time has a slight antihistaminic activity⁵. In spite of such valuable applications, enough work has not been done on such compounds. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to synthesize some 5, 6 or 7-substituted 3-phenyl-3(N,N-substituted aminomethyl)-2(3H)-benzofuranones and screen them for pharmacological properties. This communication deals with the results of this investigation.

Six different 3-phenyl-2(3H)-benzofuranones (III) with a substituent at 5, 6 or 7-position have been synthesized by condensing mandelic acid (II) with appropriate phenols (I) in the presence of concentrated sulphuric acid⁶⁻⁷.

Taking advantage of the labile nature of tertiary hydrogen at 3-position of 3-phenyl-2(3H)-benzofuranone⁸⁻¹¹, each of these compounds (III) has been subjected to the Mannich condensation using para-formaldehyde and a secondary amine (IV). The Mannich bases, 5, 6 or 7-substituted-3-phenyl-3(N,N-substituted aminomethyl)-2(3H)-benzofuranones (V) thus obtained have been purified by recrystallisation from alcohol and characterized by their analytical, ir and pmr data.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 257 spectrophotometer in nujol. PMR spectra were run on a Varian A-60 D instrument using TMS as the internal standard.

NOTES

Scheme 1

TABLE I—PHYSICAL, ANALYTICAL AND PHARMACOLOGICAL DATA OF 5, 6 OR 7-SUBSTITUTED-3-PHENYL-2-(N,N-SUBSTITUTED AMINOMETHYL)-2(3H)-BENZOFURANONES

Compound No.	R_1 (in V)	R_2	m.p. °C	% Nitrogen Found/(Calcd.)	Hypnotic activity		Anticonvulsant activity
					Mean Hypnosis + S.E. (min)	P	
1.	$R_3=R_4=R_5=H$ Morpholino		168	4.56 (4.53)	147 ± 34.03	0.05	0.0
2.	Ph	Ph	260	3.80 (3.84)	3384 ± 36.70	0.01	100.0
3.	Piperizino		280	9.12 (9.08)	141 ± 36.40	0.05	20.0
4.	$R_3=Cl; R_4=R_5=H$ Morpholino		243	4.02 (4.07)	236 ± 36.60	0.01	100.0
5.	Piperidino		218	4.13 (4.10)	106 ± 12.90	0.05	0.0
6.	<i>iso</i> -Bu	<i>iso</i> -Bu	248	3.66 (3.63)	158 ± 36.60	0.05	80.0
7.	Piperizino		302	8.22 (8.18)	254 ± 28.70	0.01	0.0
8.	$R_3=NO_2; R_4=R_5=H$ Morpholino		150	7.91 (7.89)	198 ± 54.00	0.05	20.0
9.	Cyclohexyl	Cyclohexyl	298	6.30 (6.25)	200 ± 40.00	0.05	100.0
10.	Ph	Ph	245	6.01 (6.04)	129 ± 19.80	0.05	100.0
11.	$R_3=CH_3; R_4=R_5=H$ Me	Me	120	4.99 (4.88)	133 ± 19.80	0.05	0.0
12.	<i>n</i> -Bu	<i>n</i> -Bu	253	3.87 (3.88)	142 ± 10.97	0.05	0.0
13.	Piperidino		234	4.89 (4.86)	124 ± 26.00	0.05	100.0
14.	<i>n</i> -Pr	<i>n</i> -Pr	256	4.12 (4.15)	125 ± 11.90	0.05	80.0
15.	Ph	Ph	218	3.27 (3.23)	256 ± 9.10	0.01	100.0
16.	$R_3=R_4=H; R_5=CH_3$ Cyclohexyl	Cyclohexyl	302	3.32 (3.35)	177 ± 21.00	0.05	100.0
17.	Ph	Ph	230	3.26 (3.23)	162 ± 25.40	0.05	75.0
18.	Piperizino		298	8.72 (8.69)	222 ± 42.90	0.05	25.0
19.	$R_3=R_4=H; R_5=NH_2$ Morpholino		140	8.60 (8.64)	241 ± 55.75	0.05	0.0
20.	Cyclohexyl	Cyclohexyl	299	6.72 (6.69)	216 ± 18.40	0.01	100.0
21.	Ph	Ph	238	6.41 (6.45)	196 ± 44.35	0.05	100.0
22.	Piperizino		294	15.58 (15.53)	155 ± 7.35	0.01	40.0

PMR spectrum (DMSO- d_6) of compound 11: δ 2.15 (s, 3H, Ar-CH₃), 3.18 [s, 6H, -N(CH₃)₂], 4.05 (s, 2H, C-CH₃-N), 6.98-7.46 (m, 8H, aromatic).

5, 6 or 7-Substituted-3-phenyl-2(3H)-benzofuranones (III) were synthesised by reported methods⁶⁻⁷.

General procedure for the synthesis of 5, 6 or 7-substituted-3-phenyl-3(N,N-substituted aminomethyl)-2(3H)-benzofuranones (V₁₋₂₂): 3-Phenyl-2(3H)-benzofuranone (III) (0.002 mol) was stirred with para-formaldehyde (0.003 mol), conc. hydrochloric acid (2 ml) and appropriate secondary base (IV) (0.002 mol) in absolute alcohol for 30 min. Dry hydrogen chloride gas was bubbled through the reaction mixture for at least 20 min and then the mixture refluxed on a steam bath for 1-2 h. The reaction mixture was left overnight in ice. The product (V) was precipitated with dry acetone-ether (1:1 mixture) and recrystallised from alcohol.

Moderate to high yields (55-85%) of the products were recorded. Melting points and nitrogen content of the compounds are given in Table 1.

Pharmacological screening:-----

Albino mice were employed for pharmacological screening of the compounds prepared. All the experiments were conducted in triplicate and the mean values were taken.

(a) **Gross behavioural changes in mice:** Albino mice weighing 20-40 g each received intraperitoneally a suspension of each compound at the dose of 100 mg/kg. A few of the compounds under investigation could produce mild sedation and loss of righting reflex at this dose.

(b) **Hypnotic activity:** The compounds were screened for hypnotic activity by employing the standard method¹². The test compounds were administered to the mice intraperitoneally at a dose of 100 mg/kg and the effect on barbiturate hypnosis was recorded. The results are given in Table 1.

(c) **Anticonvulsant activity (MES):** Albino rats were screened for hind limb extensor after maximal electroshock (150 mA for 0.2 sec). Dilation was effective (78% protection) at the dose of 30 mg/kg. The test compounds, each at 100 mg/kg, were administered intraperitoneally. The results are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The ir spectra of 5, 6 or 7-substituted 3-phenyl-2(3H)-benzofuranones (III) showed a strong absorption in the 1790-1785 cm⁻¹ region. The higher carbonyl stretching vibration may be due to the β,γ -unsaturated γ -lactone system characteristic of 3-substituted-2(3H)-benzofuranones¹⁸. The pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) of compounds (III) showed signals at δ 6.04-6.12 (s, 1H) and δ 7.08-7.67 (multiplet) assignable to the proton at 3-position and to aromatic protons, respectively.

The ir spectra of the Mannich bases (V) showed absorption in the 1770-1755 cm⁻¹ region indicating the carbonyl absorption shifting to lower frequency. The pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) of compounds (V) exhibited signals at δ 4.05-4.17 (s, 2H) due to

-C-CH₂-N and at δ 6.98-7.46 assignable to aromatic protons. They showed the absence of the signal due to C₃-proton, observed in compound (III), confirming its substitution.

Perusal of Table 1 reveals that of the 22 compounds tested on gross behavioural changes in mice, 12 compounds (2, 4, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 13, 14, 17, 20 and 21) produced chronic convulsions. Almost all the compounds could produce a significant sedation indicating their CNS depressant activity. The results of the hypnotic activity test indicate that 12 compounds (2, 4, 7, 8, 9, 15, 16, 18, 19, 20, 21 and 22) significantly potentiated barbiturate hypnosis, while compound 5 significantly decreased the same. Twelve compounds (2, 4, 6, 9, 10, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 20 and 21) have been found to possess significant anticonvulsant activity against electroshock seizure test.

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References

1. R. JAMES and G. ALBERT, *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.*, 1944, **131**, 85.
2. R. K. RICHARDS, G. M. EVERETT and K. E. KUSTER, *J. Pharmacol.*, 1945, **38**, 387.
3. A. W. WESTON and W. M. BROWNELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 563.
4. A. W. WESTON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 980.
5. A. BISTRZYCKI and J. FLATAU, *Chem. Ber.*, 1895, **28**, 989.
6. A. BISTRZYCKI and F. V. WEBER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1910, **43**, 2496.
7. H. V. LEIBIG, *Chem. Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 1644.
8. J. N. CHATTERJEA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **33**, 175.
9. H. E. ZAUGG, D. A. DUNNIGAM, R. J. MICHAELS, JR., R. J. SWETT, T. S. WANG, A. H. SOMMERS and R. W. DENET, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 644.
10. A. SCHONBERG and A. MUSTAFA, *Chem. Rev.*, 1947, **40**, 181.
11. L. E. SMITH and R. N. HURD, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, **22**, 588.
12. R. A. TURNER, "Screening Methods in Pharmacology", Academic Press, N. Y., 1965, Vol. 1, p. 129.
13. W. H. WASHBURN, *Appl. Spectroscop.*, 1964, **18**, 61.

Studies on 4-Thiazolidinones. Part-I: Preparation and *in vitro* Antitubercular Activity of 4,4'-Bis-(2-Aryl-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinon-3-yl)-3,3'-Dimethyl biphenyl

B. R. PAREKH, N. A. LANGALIA and K. A. THAKER
Department of Chemistry, Bhavnagar University,
Bhavnagar-364 002

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THIAZOLIDINONES with various structural modifications possess diverse biological activities and numerous reports highlighting the chemistry and